

POLITICAL SCIENCES

UKRAINIAN-CANADIAN PARLIAMENTARY DIPLOMACY: NAVIGATING THE CHALLENGES OF THE ONGOING WAR WITH RUSSIA

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the importance of Ukrainian-Canadian parliamentary cooperation during the ongoing war in Ukraine with Russia, focusing on the challenges faced and the role of Canadian Parliament in addressing the situation. The implementation of the "Parliament and Accountability of the Security Sector in Ukraine" (PASS Ukraine) project has fostered closer ties between Canadian and Ukrainian Members of Parliament (MPs) and facilitated communication channels.

Furthermore, the article highlights the significance of the Ukrainian topic in Canadian Parliament speeches. It notes that Ukraine has been a recurring subject of discussion, particularly during critical moments in Ukraine's history, such as the Russian invasion in 2014 and the ongoing war. Canadian MPs have expressed their support for Ukraine, condemned Russian aggression, and advocated for measures to protect Ukraine's sovereignty and assist in its recovery.

The article underscores the breadth of topics related to Ukraine that have been addressed in Canadian Parliament speeches. These topics include humanitarian assistance, economic support, political reforms, and the promotion of democracy in Ukraine. The active engagement of Ukrainian Canadians in advocating for Ukrainian issues has further contributed to the prominence of the Ukrainian topic in parliamentary discussions.

The article suggests referring to official records, transcripts, and speeches available through the official website of the Canadian Parliament for a comprehensive understanding of the discussions and importance of the Ukrainian topic in Canadian parliamentary debates. It concludes by emphasizing the ongoing attention given to Ukraine within the Canadian Parliament and the commitment of Canadian MPs to supporting Ukraine's stability, democracy, and territorial integrity.

Keywords: Ukraine, Canada, parliamentary diplomacy, ongoing war in Ukraine, Russia-Ukraine conflict, parliamentary cooperation, PASS Ukraine, democratic governance, legislative strengthening, parliamentary oversight, women's political participation, electoral reforms, knowledge exchange, public awareness.

The main problem for Ukrainian-Canadian parliamentary diplomacy during the ongoing war in Ukraine with Russia is the challenge of effectively addressing the complexities and dynamics of the conflict while navigating international relations and balancing domestic interests. Since February 24, 2022, the Ukrainian-Canadian parliamentary cooperation has been strengthened through the implementation of the "Parliament and Accountability of the Security Sector in Ukraine" (PASS Ukraine) project. This project, supported by Global Affairs Canada and implemented by the Parliamentary Centre and the Agency for Legislative Initiatives, has played a crucial role in fostering closer ties between Canadian and Ukrainian Members of Parliament (MPs) and facilitating communication channels during the onset of the war.

The Parliamentary Centre Canada, an independent non-profit organization based in Canada, has established a direct institutional relationship with the Ukrainian Parliament (Verkhovna Rada) to support parliamentary development in Ukraine [2]. The significance of this cooperation can be understood through various key points:

Democratic Governance and Capacity Building: The Parliamentary Centre has been actively involved in promoting democratic governance and enhancing the institutional capacity of the Ukrainian Parliament. Through tailored programs, it has supported the development of transparent, accountable, and effective parliamentary processes, procedures, and structures.

Legislative Strengthening: By facilitating initiatives to strengthen legislative processes, the Parliamentary Centre has provided technical assistance, training, and expertise to Ukrainian MPs and parliamentary staff. This support has focused on areas such as legislative drafting, policy analysis, and committee work, ensuring the development of robust legislative frameworks.

Parliamentary Oversight and Accountability: Enhancing the Ukrainian Parliament's capacity for effective oversight and promoting accountability has been a priority for the Parliamentary Centre. It has worked closely with the Verkhovna Rada to develop mechanisms for parliamentary monitoring, evaluation, and scrutiny of government actions, thus ensuring transparency and accountability in governance.

Women's Political Participation and Gender Equality: Promoting gender equality and increasing women's political participation has been a key focus of the Parliamentary Centre's work in Ukraine. Through its initiatives, it has supported efforts to enhance the representation of women in the Ukrainian Parliament, encourage gender-responsive legislation, and strengthen the capacity of female parliamentarians.

Electoral Reforms and Democratic Processes: The Parliamentary Centre has contributed to electoral reforms and the promotion of democratic processes in Ukraine. By providing technical assistance and expertise in areas such as electoral legislation, electoral systems, and electoral administration, it has helped

strengthen the integrity and inclusivity of the electoral process.

Knowledge Exchange and Networking: The Parliamentary Centre has facilitated knowledge exchange and networking opportunities between the Ukrainian Parliament and other parliaments worldwide. This has included organizing workshops, conferences, and study visits to promote the sharing of best practices, experiences, and lessons learned in parliamentary development.

From March 31 to April 2 2022, PASS Ukraine, in collaboration with Global Affairs Canada, played a vital role in organizing and supporting a visit to Ottawa by five senior female Ukrainian MPs. This visit served as an opportunity for high-level engagements with Canadian government and parliamentary officials, demonstrating the significance of Ukrainian-Canadian parliamentary cooperation. The Ukrainian delegation had the privilege of meeting with esteemed individuals including the Prime Minister, Deputy Prime Minister, Minister of Foreign Affairs, Minister of International Development, Members of the House of Commons Foreign Affairs Committee, Members of the Canada-Ukraine Friendship Group in the Canadian Parliament, and Senators [1].

During these meetings, the Ukrainian legislators conveyed their perspectives on the ongoing war, emphasizing the profound impact of Russian atrocities and alleged war crimes on Ukrainian women. Their consistent message expressed gratitude for Canada's support for Ukraine thus far while making an appeal for increased assistance in addressing the challenges faced by Ukraine.

In addition to facilitating this important visit, PASS Ukraine also organized two international dialogues that provided a platform for Ukrainian MPs to lead insightful discussions. The focus of these dialogues was on the consequences of the war and the difficulties of promoting democracy in a conflict-ravaged Ukraine. The events brought together a total of 17 MPs, 15 parliamentary staff members, and 5 Senators from 18 countries. This gathering of international representatives fostered an invaluable exchange of ideas and perspectives, contributing to a better understanding of the situation in Ukraine and the challenges it faces.

PASS Ukraine's efforts extended beyond these direct engagements, as they actively worked to raise public awareness about the situation in Ukraine among millions of Canadians. They organized press conferences and facilitated print, radio, and TV interviews featuring Ukrainian MPs and human rights defenders. Notably, PASS Ukraine collaborated with the Centre for Civil Liberties, which was awarded the 2022 Nobel Peace Prize, further amplifying their influence and the importance of their message. The engagement on social media platforms further increased the reach and impact of their activities, ensuring that the situation in Ukraine was brought to the attention of a wide audience.

Overall, PASS Ukraine's initiatives and collaborations have played a crucial role in strengthening Ukrainian-Canadian parliamentary cooperation and raising awareness about the challenges faced by Ukraine, particularly in the context of the ongoing war.

Parliamentary Speeches mentions Ukraine

The importance of the Ukrainian topic in Canadian Parliament speeches can vary depending on various factors, including current events, political priorities, and international relations. However, it is worth noting that Ukraine has been a significant topic of discussion in the Canadian Parliament over the years, particularly in relation to issues such as Ukraine's sovereignty, territorial integrity, human rights, and democratic development.

During critical moments in Ukraine's history, such as the Russian invasion in 2014 and the ongoing War in Ukraine, the Ukrainian topic has received significant attention in Canadian Parliament speeches. Members of Parliament (MPs) have expressed their support for Ukraine, condemned Russian aggression, and advocated for measures to protect Ukraine's sovereignty and assist in its recovery. In addition to discussing the conflict, Canadian Parliament speeches have often focused on topics such as humanitarian assistance, economic support, political reforms, and the promotion of democracy in Ukraine. MPs have also highlighted the importance of Canada-Ukraine relations, including trade, cultural exchanges, and people-to-people connections [4].

Moreover, Ukrainian Canadians, who make up a significant portion of the Canadian population, have been vocal in advocating for Ukrainian issues in the Canadian Parliament. Their engagement and activism have contributed to the prominence of the Ukrainian topic in parliamentary discussions. It is important to recognize that the level of attention given to the Ukrainian topic can vary over time and depending on the specific circumstances. It is advisable to refer to official records, transcripts, and speeches available through the official website of the Canadian Parliament to gain a comprehensive understanding of the discussions and importance of the Ukrainian topic in Canadian parliamentary debates.

Since the first day of the 44th Canadian Parliament, the Ukrainian topic has been extensively discussed, with a total of 1565 mentions. This highlights the significant attention and interest that Canadian Members of Parliament (MPs) have dedicated to Ukraine-related issues [4].

In addition to the Ukrainian topic, Canadian MPs have engaged in discussions on a range of other important subjects. The topic of "Russia" has been brought up 1311 times, indicating a keen interest in the geopolitical dynamics and war in Ukraine. The mention of "War" in parliamentary discussions stands at 1099 times, reflecting the ongoing Ukrainian and international security concerns that have garnered attention from Canadian MPs.

The issue of "Refugees" has been addressed 311 times, underscoring the humanitarian aspect of global crises and Canada's commitment to offering refuge and assistance to Ukraine in need. The topic of "Oil and Gas" has been mentioned 257 times, highlighting the significance of energy resources and related policies in the Canadian Parliament's debates.

Furthermore, discussions on "Pipeline Transformation" have taken place 213 times, indicating the importance of energy infrastructure and the need for sustainable and environmentally conscious solutions. The topic of "International Conflict" and "International

Conflict Resolution" has been raised 202 times, demonstrating Canada's engagement in global peacekeeping efforts and diplomatic resolutions to conflicts worldwide.

Figure 1. Frequency of mentions Ukrainian topic in Canadian Parliament

These figures reflect the diverse range of topics and issues that Canadian MPs address in the 44th Canadian Parliament, demonstrating the breadth of their responsibilities and the global perspective they bring to their parliamentary duties. The high number of mentions related to Ukraine highlights the significance of Canada's engagement with Ukrainian affairs and the

country's commitment to supporting Ukraine in its pursuit of stability, democracy, and territorial integrity.

In addition to the frequency of mentions, it is interesting to observe the various orders of business in the Canadian Parliament where the Ukrainian topic has been discussed. The breakdown is as follows:

Figure 2. Canadian Parliament Discussed topic : Ukraine

Government Orders: The Ukrainian topic has been addressed during Government Orders 1219 times. This indicates that the Canadian government has actively engaged in discussions and initiatives related to Ukraine, demonstrating its commitment to the relationship between the two countries.

Oral Question Period: Members of Parliament have raised the Ukrainian topic during the Oral Question Period 601 times. This signifies the significance of Ukraine-related issues in the parliamentary dialogue, with MPs seeking clarification and accountability from government officials on matters pertaining to Ukraine.

Routine Proceedings: Discussions on the Ukrainian topic have taken place during Routine Proceedings

421 times. This highlights the ongoing attention given to Ukraine within the regular parliamentary procedures, where various matters are presented and discussed.

Statements by Members: Canadian MPs have made statements about the Ukrainian topic 171 times. This particular order of business allows MPs to express their views, share important information, or pay tribute to significant events or individuals. The frequency of statements demonstrates the active engagement of MPs in highlighting Ukrainian matters to the parliamentary community.

Adjournment Proceedings: The Ukrainian topic has been brought up during Adjournment Proceedings 101 times. This phase of the parliamentary session provides an opportunity for MPs to raise specific concerns or seek clarification on issues before the session concludes for the day.

Private Members Business: The Ukrainian topic has been discussed in the context of Private Members Business 56 times. This indicates that individual MPs have taken the initiative to address Ukrainian matters through private members' bills or motions, showcasing their personal commitment to Ukraine-related issues.

Appendix: The Ukrainian topic has appeared in the Appendix section 17 times. This section typically includes additional documents, reports, or information relevant to the parliamentary proceedings. The Ukrainian topic's presence in the Appendix suggests that there have been specific documents or reports related to Ukraine that have been referred to or included in the parliamentary record.

Emergency Debate: Discussions related to the Ukrainian topic have led to Emergency Debates being held 14 times. This underscores the urgency and importance attached to Ukraine-related issues, prompting dedicated debates within the parliamentary framework.

Speech from the Throne: The Ukrainian topic has been referenced during the Speech from the Throne on 8 occasions. This highlights that the government's official agenda, as outlined in the Speech from the Throne, has included matters related to Ukraine.

Orders of the Day: The Ukrainian topic has been discussed during Orders of the Day 5 times. Orders of the Day typically involve the consideration of specific bills, motions, or business items scheduled for a particular day's parliamentary session.

These statistics reveal the wide range of parliamentary orders of business where the Ukrainian topic has been addressed, demonstrating the significant attention and importance accorded to Ukraine-related matters in the Canadian Parliament.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the implementation of the "Parliament and Accountability of the Security Sector in Ukraine" (PASS Ukraine) project since February 24, 2022, has strengthened Ukrainian-Canadian parliamentary cooperation. This project, supported by Global Affairs Canada and implemented by the Parliamentary Centre and the Agency for Legislative Initiatives, has facilitated closer ties between Canadian and Ukrainian Members of Parliament (MPs) and fostered effective communication channels during the onset of the war.

The collaboration between the Parliamentary Centre Canada, an independent non-profit organization, and the Ukrainian Parliament (Verkhovna Rada) has been instrumental in promoting democratic governance and enhancing the institutional capacity of the Ukrainian Parliament. Through tailored programs, the Parliamentary Centre has supported the development of transparent, accountable, and effective parliamentary processes, procedures, and structures. This includes initiatives focused on legislative strengthening, parliamentary oversight, accountability, women's political participation, gender equality, electoral reforms, democratic processes, and knowledge exchange.

The visit of five senior female Ukrainian MPs to Ottawa, organized and supported by PASS Ukraine in collaboration with Global Affairs Canada, further exemplifies the commitment to Ukrainian-Canadian parliamentary cooperation. High-level meetings with Canadian government and parliamentary officials provided a platform for the Ukrainian delegation to share their perspectives on the ongoing war and emphasize the impact on Ukrainian women. PASS Ukraine also facilitated international dialogues, bringing together MPs, parliamentary staff members, and Senators from 18 countries, to discuss the consequences of the war and challenges in promoting democracy in Ukraine.

PASS Ukraine's efforts extended beyond direct engagements, as they actively raised public awareness about the situation in Ukraine among millions of Canadians. Through press conferences, interviews, and social media engagement, they amplified the influence and importance of the Ukrainian topic, collaborating with notable organizations such as the Centre for Civil Liberties. Overall, PASS Ukraine's initiatives and collaborations have played a crucial role in strengthening Ukrainian-Canadian parliamentary cooperation and raising awareness about the challenges faced by Ukraine, particularly in the context of the ongoing war.

The Ukrainian topic has been prominently discussed in Canadian Parliament speeches, with a significant number of mentions, indicating the importance attached to Ukraine-related issues. The topic has been addressed across various orders of business, demonstrating the wide-ranging attention given to Ukraine within the parliamentary dialogue. These collective efforts contribute to supporting Ukraine's sovereignty, democracy, and territorial integrity while fostering a strong partnership between Canada and Ukraine.

References

1. Agency for legislative initiatives <https://parliament.org.ua/en/home-us/>
2. Parliamentary center <https://www.parlcent.org/fr/>
3. Verkhovna Rada Committee on Foreign Policy and Interparliamentary Cooperation <https://komzak.rada.gov.ua/uploads/documents/30814.pdf>
4. Canadian Parliamentary Debates (Hansard) <https://www.ourcommons.ca/PublicationSearch/en/?targetLang=&Text=ukraine>